

<p>On the Matters of the Phonosyntactics</p>		<p>Linguistics</p> <p>Keywords: phonosyntactics, prosodics, statistic data, sillabeme, acenteme, intoneme, syntacsema, grammema.</p>
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<p>Abstract</p>		
<p>The article elucidates the issues of prosody in phonetics. The field of prosody is not thoroughly investigated among phonetics researches in the world linguistics. The majority of the researches is dedicated to the segmental units of the field. The special attention is given to the forming of the scientific views of the theory of prosody in Uzbek linguistics. The terms and events related to prosody constitute opposed paradigm with the language and speech units. The supersegmental units are studied as the object of the research of phonetics and linguistics layers. The phonosyntactic features of the stress are shown. The development of the field of prosody is substantiated on the bases of the theoretical and experimental researches. The diachronic and synchronic differences concerning the experimental research of the prosodic units are shown. The acoustic-articulation features of the speech are analyzed. The examples of the experimental research of prosodic means investigated on the bases of Uzbek language materials are given. The events and notions of the natural and artificial speech are revealed. The function of the prosodic features through the artificial speech is shown. The inconsistency of supersegmental units without segmental units is scientifically proved. The syntagmatic relationships of the segmental units serve to reveal the prosodic means. The intonation and its related matters are investigated. The terms as the logical stress, intonation construction or intoneme take a central place among the notions of the theory of prosody and phonosyntactics. The variants of intoneme are defined through the realization of the intonation components in a speech and are explained through the examples of fiction. Being related to the propositional structure the intonation timbre provides the utterance with the various shade and coloring. The new contents of the field are defined by the scientific conclusions based on the experiments' results in the field of prosody. The theoretical issues of phonetics-syntax, syntactic intonation, intonation of syntactic units, intonation constructions and intonemes are considered.</p>		

The theoretical matters of phonetics have been elucidated regularly in scientific resources. One of the most significant matters of phonetics to the linguistics is the prosodics, this field is unique since it has been rarely studied scientifically. The peculiarities of prosodics and materials related to it have been referred to as one of the main branches of the phonetics in foreign scientific sources, moreover, not only on researches of the field, but even textbooks also have some special space for the matters of prosodics. It has been observed that authors of majority of textbooks of Uzbek linguistics have not paid enough attention to the prosodics and matters relating to this field, the reasons of this can be pointed as lack of researches into the field of experimental research of super segment units, researches which have been carried out under traditional circumstance, no publication of clear and firm scientific conclusions owing to the shortage of statistic date in the sphere, not carrying out researches into phonetics based on modern electronic programs and the effect of constant changes procedures in language to the surface of the language.

Moreover, in this very field of linguistics the matters relating to the theory of intonation or prosodics have not been added to the daily routine as peak issues of researches in this field yet. Therefore, in Uzbek linguistics, there is a demand to form a single scientific view in this field of subject, fulfill theoretical researches which have monographic characteristics in the domain of intonation.

New ideas and views which are given in some researches as fundamentals of the field of prosodics theory and exposing theoretical matters which are based on the new researching ways, counting them in accordance with their directions, differentiating some typical matters, marking the place of the theoretical researches within the language layers are general purpose of the article.

The theory of prosodics is distinguishable in phonetic-phonologic section with its several issues. In sum, prosodics does not exist without language units, it creates opposition paradigm towards segmental units, as other linguistic means, super segmental units are also made up a single structure as system, therefore, they are divided into certain elements and connected with each other with peculiar functions. The essence of researches based on prosodics theory is generalized in science under the name of phonosyntactics. Prosodic units, as units of upper and lower layer units of the language, are divided into language and speech phenomenon, the views of F. De Saussure have been seen as fundamentals in this case. Terms belonging to the system of prosodics make up a contradictory paradigm to language and speech units. This area consists of its own of terminological machine; the objects belonging to the research are connected to one another in terms of essence. Scientific conclusions, which are results of experimental research, are also considered as one of the most important parts of the subject since they are main pointer of the field. Indeed, prosodics is directly connected to fields of linguistics, such as, phonetics, syntax and stylistics and characterized as the main object of researches in these fields. We can conclude from the information mentioned above as follows while studying prosodic intermediaries carrying out experimental researches and concluding with scientific precise information, studying super segmental units theoretically, finding out about their functional, semantic, syntactic, and stylistic peculiarities give a chance to imagine the object of research of this field.

Nowadays the scientific investigations and dissertations, the problem matters in the articles, the novelty of the topic, and the effectiveness of the results carried out mainly in the spheres of the natural and exact sciences are realized through experimental researches. The scientific inferences obtained by the way of experimental researches are shown by figures and facts. In this perspective, conducting the experimental research in social-humanitarian sciences, mainly in the domain of philology, and comparing the results, obtained by traditional experimental research will further objective solution of the existing problems in the science. Furthermore, the topic novelty and facts reliability will create the opportunity to implement the obtained scientific inferences into practice.

In the history of Uzbek linguistics the experimental research related to prosody or intonation patterns were carried out and a number of the results were achieved. However, the traditional methods and the speech with its acoustic-articulation features recorded on a tape and intonographs of the former Soviet period were analyzed in the experimental research. The results of the given analyses served to revealing the features of speech sounds and showing the features peculiar to supersegmental units. The experimental research carried out by the traditional methods promotes to form the branch of acoustic phonetics in Uzbek and other languages.

The results of the experimental research carried out by the traditional ways were reflected in contemporary scientific literature.[3] We do not claim that they are wrong, but their significant differences are striking. The differences of the figures show the influence on the theories related to this branch of linguistics. For example, the time spent for the utterance ‘jallod’ was equal to 930 msec. The current experiment results revealed the time spent for the utterance is 572 msec.

The results of the current experiment concerning the acoustic features of the speech signals showed the considerable discrepancy in comparison with the traditional experiment results devoted to the speech elements. Therefore, there is a need to conduct the experimental research and analyze the acoustic features of speech signals in Uzbek language. The scientific conclusions based on the exact figures effort the opportunity to fresh judgments on the theories in the branch of prosody. Accordingly, there is a necessity to analyze the time spent to speech parts, the degree of the change of the voice, sound amplitude, and the sound hertz by computer programs and on the bases of the results obtained to make the scientific inferences. In defining the issues of acoustic phonetics, prosody and intonation it is expedient to determine the artificial and natural speech. The artificial speech can be formed with the help of computer technologies. The elements of intonation in the artificial speech are not so striking. Regarding the syntagmatic relationships between the sounds are not similar to the natural ones, the intonation suitable to the language is not revealed. The most significant conclusion is that the intonation cannot be formed without syntagmatic relationships of segmental units. It can be seen from the recorded speech sounds, which are located next to each other, the chain is not formed and intonation rhythm in the speech cannot exist. Thus, the prosodic features are peculiar to the natural speech and are formed on the bases of syntagmatic relationships of the segmental units.

On upper layers of the language, it can be seen that the essence of any kind of research is elucidated based on invariant and variant structures. It should be acknowledged that in most of researches which are super segmental and belong to the phonetic-phonologic layer, its units are being overlooked on the matters of elucidating syntagmatic-paradigmatic peculiarities. Similarly, it is stated that in researches which are devoted to prosodic means, they need to be analyzed in accordance with the principal of occurrences of language and speech. In this case, it should be specifically shown that even larger units of phonetic-phonologic area, as in upper layer units of language, are seen under a single paradigm circle. Therefore, main attention should be drawn to the intoneme matter which can elucidate the essence of prosodic research. This kind of approach to the matter is reasonable that language units like sillabeme, acenteme, and intoneme in prosodic field paradigm, since they are related to syntactic units, phonosyntactic researches should be carried out. Like any kind of linguistic units, prosodic components too, they are also associated with certain paradigmatic structures in human memory. Components of super segmental units are formed in human imagination and serve to differentiate linguistic units in terms of semantic and grammar structure. Particularly, it can be observed that intonation and its components are associated in speech via the pronunciation of segmental units. The speaker expresses information in speech using language units; this information is made through language units. Intonation also serves to enrich the meaning of information by its own communicative function. In this condition, in speech change of the voice timbre, whether it is high or low impact on the meaning of information. That is why, expressing ones opinion via voice is seen in fiction literature materials, it can be seen in expressions given by the words of author, such as: “he spoke bluntly”, “threatening was obvious from his voice”, “trembling in his voice was the sign of fear”.

Being related to the speech tempo, the phonation means are analyzed among the linguistic units. The second property of the phonation means is their analyses within the units of the paradigmatic rows. According to the Russian linguist G.V.Kolshanskiy the phonation features of the speech are also considered in the paralinguistic features or paralinguisms. Giving the additional information and being close to the speech means the gestures, miming and some others are included in nonverbal means [7, 33]. The peculiar feature of a person’s articulation is in forming two structures simultaneously in the process of rise of the utterance. The former structure is a linguistic, materialized through the phonetic units, the latter are paralinguistic structures, comprising nonlinguistic units and materialized with the help of the sound. The interval between the formal and semantic structures of the both units can be called phonation means.

It is believed, the phonation means belong to the communication units, which are considered to be the meanings, formed with the help of speech organs and the person’s sound timbre. Pretending that the linguistic units in the sound intonation are not so important, they can be referred to linguistics, while the lack of a gesture and miming in the sound intonation structure can be close to paralinguistic means. Thus, the phonation means can be considered as a separate form of paralinguistic units.

In this place, phonation means matters are also added to the phonosyntactic researches. Phonation means are close to intonation from one prospective, while they are close to paralinguistics from another point. It should be specifically mentioned that in this case phonation means also join to the intonation structure and serve to increase expressiveness of speech. At this very moment, we can witness joining of intonation and phonation means with one another.

There is also a need to define the features of categories of the similar problems set in the given article. In other words, it should be clarified if the logical stress is syntactic or semantic category of the sentence. Moreover, it should be identified to what extent the intonation structure or intoneme can be referred to the branch of actual division. In addition to it, the intonation deals with the study of the speech events, while the intoneme can be analyzed in the semantic or syntactic category. It can be concluded from the abovementioned the actual division of the sentence and intonation constructions belong to the syntax from one side and considered as the problems of syntax. However, the only general feature related to both of the issues is a scientific paradigm or prosody which connects the two problems. Therefore, the terms phonetic syntax or syntactic phonetics are used towards both of the phenomena and serve to analyze the syntactic phenomena phonetic-phonologically or among the supersegmental paradigms and provide their interrelations. Generally, the notion of prosody shows that the two branches can be a part of one scientific context and serves to reveal the existence of the integral and distinguishing features. The reason of it is that any researcher within his scientific work is a main issue of the logical stress and the theory of prosody related to the actual division of the sentence. However, the problems of the intonation construction and actualization are not differentiated in the study of prosody and their general features are not achieved. The two features of the prosodic problems are not analyzed in the scientific literature. Though the object of their research is the same, but the different contradicting functions are not substantiated. Having the semantic category and being related to the actual division of the sentence, the logical stress serves to reveal the communicative aspect of the sentence. The intonation construction peculiar to the sentence acquires the paradigmatic features referring to the syntactic categories and has a function of distinguishing the communicative type of the sentence. Logically the intonation construction takes a central place among the theory of prosody or phonosyntactics. The majority of the researches related to the branch of prosody give an impetus to form the aspect of the new phonosyntactics based on the dichotomy of the language and speech.

Indeed, the materials of fiction literature or the speech of the main hero, since it is related to the context, meaning which are being expressed via speech pronunciation or intonation should be noted as variants of intoneme. Actually, the term intoneme is typical with the terms of syntaxeme and grammeme which serves to mark grammar structure of syntactic units. The syntaxeme differentiates the peculiarity of consolidating word phrase, sentence and units given in it, it is needed to distinguish whether the sentence belongs to government, agreement or fusion according to syntactic meaning. Affirmative and interrogative intonation intonemes are formed.

These types of sentences are known as intonation constructions in science. Intoneme and intonation constructions are used together; they can be used as synonymous terms. However, they have not always served to define a single term or a term of the same sphere. If tone or the intonation affects the grammar structure in construction composition, these terms serve under a paradigm circle. Especially these matters are acknowledged as language and speech occurrences.

Intonema exists as language unit; it is expressed as speech occurrence via components of intonation. Intonation is formed while speech mainly segmental units structure. In logical assumption, it is impossible to mind about intonation without segmental units. The tremble of voice is component of intonation. It appears in high or low form depending on the speech condition.

For instance,

Овозим баландлаб кетди шекилли, ичкаридан башанг кийинган йигит чиқди.

- Нима гап, акахон?

...Йигит гапимни диққат билан тинглади. Кейин овозини пастлатиб сўради:

- Қайси аптекадан олдингиз, акахон?

...Тўғриси айтсам йигитчада инсоф бор экан.

- Одамни қийнаманг, ака! – деди ерга қараб. – Нима қилайлик, бизниям «точкаларимиз» бор. Харажатларимиз бор. Акахонларимиз бор... (Ў.Ҳошимов Дафтар ҳошиясидаги битиклар).

(Seems like my voice had become loud, a man who dressed foppish came out.

- What is up, bro?

... The young man listened to my words carefully. Then he asked lowering his voice:

- from which chemist's did you purchase, bro?

... Honestly, the young man was fair.

- Please, don't suffer a man, bro! – He said looking down at the ground. – What should we do, we also have our "points". We have expanses. We have brothers... (O'.Hoshimov Daftar hoshiyasidagi bitiklar- Scripts on edges of notebook.)

Models of intonation are present via expressions which come to existence during speech process. In speech structure, speakers comprehend one another through real intonations. In propositions which are expressed via speech fear, hesitation, excitement, anger, threatening, happiness and such kind of speech acts are admitted as the result of intonation. Such kinds of meanings are not present in units of language, but they appear in various intonations and tones to serve providing certain color and variety to the speech. In this case, phonation intermediaries are very important. Pronouncing the word Ahmad in 16 different intonations also proves this idea. One of the intermediaries which provide colorfulness is considered to be voice treble.

The pace of speech tempo, whether it is fast or slow, whether the pause is long or short, the communicative purpose which is related to placement of segment units with logical stress to the

predicative structure of language considering typological peculiarity of language and such kinds of language models serve to scientifically prove intonema as other units.

In Uzbek linguistics, one of the scientists who seriously studied matters concerning prosodic field is considered to be professor M.Mirtojiyev. Intonation and stress matters are one of the leading features of his researches. He tries to perfectly study super segmental units in his experimental researches based on traditional methods. In his views on intonation, differently than other scholars, he comes up with an idea that in the system of sentence intonation there are intonations of united parts, separated parts, callers, linking words, added sentence, and even tact. From the point of M.Mirtojiyev there are unique intonation structures in segmental units' pronunciation which belongs to all surface of language, and it is stated that they should be studied in a way which is unique to the mother tongue.

There are ideas which belong to phonosyntactic field in researches of the scholar in prosodic field, some of the ideas which are related to intonation constructions are not appropriate to agree. In particular, it is stated as "... The tremble of voice is not important in ordering sentences at all, so is in wish sentences. Only the last syllable is pronounced a bit loudly". Some views as mentioned in previous sentence such as the tremble of voice in sentence structure "not important for ordering and wish sentences" are thoughtless. The reason is the timbre or intonation timbre is not scientific proof to distinguish communicative type of the sentence. When the main idea is about syntacsema and grammema, one thing should be firmly stated that, the tone is characterized as one of the prosodic intermediaries with its differentiating function of grammar meaning which is special to syntactic units.

For instance,

Саволлар Саъдуллани ҳайратга солди. "Консултация? Тавба!"
 - *Соат иккида? Кеча айтишмовди-ку...* (М.Ҳазратқулов Чироқ ўчмаган кеча).
(Questions surprised Sa'dulla. "Consultation? Oh my God!"
 – *at two o'clock? They didn't tell yesterday... (M.Hamzatqulov Chiroq o'chmagan kecha – The night when the light wasn't off).)*

In the sentence given above, there is not any kind of grammar intermediaries to form an interrogative sentence. That is why; the intonation can be seen as the main grammar intermediary which marks the type of the sentence.

Expressing affirmative and imperative sentences is also the same as mentioned above. It is marked with punctual marks in writing.

For instance,

Консултация. Консултация! Соат иккида. Соат иккида!
(Consultation. Consultation! At two o'clock. At two o'clock!)

And the intonation timbre, mainly, belongs to the propositional structure of the sentence that it provides the sentence with various colors. These matters are also proved in the views of the

Russian linguists L.R.Zinder and N.V.Cheremsina. “expressing various emotional-expressive colors in speech, an occurrence called extra pronunciation color is timbre. *He spoke in the voice of hate, fear, happiness* can be marked as exactly color of timbre.”

In this way, researches of M.Mirtojiyev is particular to the practical linguistics system that scientific conclusions which have been gained basing on experimental results were not perfectly studied or completed completely. That is why, theoretical matters of prosodics were not finished in these works. For instance, the time spent on pronouncing a sound has been marked as millisecond time measurement in experimental researches. However, since enough statistical information was not provided basing on scientific conclusion, its theoretical fundamentals were not fully elucidated. In his point of view, syntactic functions of prosodic intermediaries which serve to form intonation construction’s syntactic functions are not discussed in prosodic matters. From this point of view, views of professor B.O’rinboyev on prosodic matter about intonation construction and his theoretical researches concerning this theme is significantly important.

It is certain that solving all the issues which are included in the content of prosodics or intonation is impossible in one or several researches. The reason of this is because issues of certain field are not analyzed based on a single viewpoint. The object of the research is chosen in accordance with the essence of the matter. The classification of a single theme circle and choosing of a topic by a group of researchers in narrow sphere is up to looking at the matter from an angle, degree of previous study, significance connection to the newly formed fields and separation of this topic from fields of the same type. That is why, even though scientific researches carried out on various themes in prosodic field create a single system in essence, they are distinguishable from inner point of view as different directions of the field. As prosodic and intonation occurrences seem to be one thing, especially in the inside of these fields there are alike typical occurrences whose common and comparative sides should be scientifically proven, history of formation shown, their comparative sides should be shown basing on fiction literature and these things are the most important part of any kind of scientific research.

In researches carried out in the field of prosodic field, typical matters which should be compared to one another have been overlooked by researchers. One of such kind of matters is logical stress, actualization, and intonation construction and comparison of these themes and themes as close as mentioned above to one another is very important to resolve many issues. Mentioned logical stress, actualization, intonation construction are characterized as belonging to the prosodic field of phonetics, yet they are not studied on the phonetic-phonologic layer units. Their important, significant peculiarity is they are distinguished as being occurrence of upper language layer in syntax and syntactic units’ structure. In this way, the object of this research is seriously different from other matters of prosodic field. In this very place, new part of the field which is related to the science, phonetic-syntax, syntactic intonation, the intonation of syntactic units, intonation constructions, intoneme and such kind of theoretical matters of field is formed.

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